

TABLE I—THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS AND STABILITY CONSTANT OF METAL—L-LYSINE MONOHYDROCHLORIDE SYSTEMS

Metal ion	Stability constants of proton/metal complexes	Temp. (°C)		-ΔG° kcal mol ⁻¹		ΔH° kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS° cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		15°	30°	15°	30°	at 30°	at 30°
Fe ^{II}	log K ₁	5.76	5.14	7.54	6.68	-22.84	-57.42
	log K ₂	2.87	2.65				
Sr ^{II}	log K ₁	5.25	5.16	6.89	7.27	+2.49	+32.90
	log K ₂	2.99	2.73				
Sb ^{III}	log K ₁	3.08	2.95	10.98	11.82	+2.13	+45.87
	log K ₂	2.86	3.20				

tion. Stability constants of metal and proton complexes were determined by using Bjerrum Calvin technique⁹. pH of the solution was measured with Metram Harisan E-520 pH meter.

Results and Discussion

The ligand dissociates as

The carboxylic group of the acid does not form the conjugate base intramolecularly, indicating practically the absence of any dipolar form. Presence of a single inflection on titrating the acid with strong base in aqueous media contributes to the foregoing view.

Examination of the pH-metric curves displayed a separation of metal—ligand curve from acid curve. This contributes to the fact that the protons liberation is due to the complexation value of $\bar{n}$ increased gradually in all cases. This amounts to the involvement of anionic form of the acid in complexation, the $\bar{n}$ value of 2 for Fe^{II} and Sr^{II} L-lysine monohydrochloride system and of 3 for Sb^{III} L-lysine monohydrochloride system indicating the presence of complexes of 1:2 and 1:3 stoichiometry, respectively. Analysis of formation curves ($\bar{n}$ vs pL) indicates that there was not much difference in the values of successive stability constants. The calculations of stepwise formation therefore could not be done by Bjerrum integral method ($\log K_1/K_2, 2.5$)⁹. Further, it was seen that the formation curves less their wave character justify the similarity in the successive formation constants. Even the system of higher complexity Sb^{III} L-lysine monohydrochloride ($\bar{n}=3$) could not fulfil the conditions, i.e. $K_1 - K_2$. (i) $\log K = -\log(L^-)$ at $\bar{n}=0.5$, (ii) $-\Delta G^\circ = RT \log K$.

The value of $-\Delta G^\circ$ for Fe^{II} decreases with the increase of temperature. Whereas the value of $-\Delta G^\circ$ for Sr^{II} and Sb^{III} L-lysine monohydrochloride system increase with the rise of temperature. The enthalpy (ΔH°) is positive for Sr^{II} and Sb^{III} L-lysine monohydrochloride system justifying the endothermic nature of these reactions. The positive

value of ΔS° for Sr^{II} and Sb^{III} only favours the formation of the complexes¹⁰. Table I contains the mean value of stability constants of metal and proton complexes at different temperatures and their thermodynamic functions.

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References

1. M. KAZMARSH and K. MARION, *Roez. Chem.*, 1973, 47, 245.
2. A. I. KOSTROMIN, *Zh. Neorg. Khim.*, 1956, 2385.
3. C. L. NORMAN and E. DOODY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2385.
4. A. AZIZKHAN and W. U. MALIK, *Curr. Sci.*, 1960, 29, 135.
5. R. PRADOS, M. STADTHER, JR. and R. BRUCE, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, 36, 689.
6. A. K. JAIN, K. D. JAIN and U. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 963.
7. A. K. JAIN, K. D. JAIN and U. SHARMA, *Indian. J. Phy. Nat. Sci., Sect. A*, 1983, 3.
8. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solutions", Hase, Copenhagen, 1941.
9. N. R. SHAH and J. R. SHAH, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 1583.
10. S. S. SAWHNEY and N. CHANDRA, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1983, 66, 369, 372.

Additive and Antagonistic Effects of Mixtures of Cationic and Anionic Surfactants in the Suppression of Positive Polarographic Maximum of Thallium(I) *vis-a-vis* the Adsorption Characteristics

(MISS) INDU BALA and MUKHTAR SINGH*

Chemistry Department, Agra College, Agra-282 002

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THOUGH several workers¹⁻³ have attempted the suppression of positive polarographic maximum of Tl^I by a number of ionic and non-ionic surfactants, no attempt has been made so far to study the suppressive behaviour of mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants in respect of positive maxima. In this paper, we report the results of our

investigations on the additive and antagonistic effects of mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants in the suppression of positive maximum of Tl^{I} . The adsorption characteristics of cationic and anionic surfactants separately as well as in their mixtures have also been studied.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The depolariser concentration was kept at $2.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. $NaNO_3$ (1.0 M) was used as the supporting electrolyte. A Toshniwal CLO2 manual polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL50 polyflex galvanometer was used for measuring the potential and current, respectively. Deoxygenation of the solutions was done by passing a steady stream of purified hydrogen through the solutions. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Throughout the measurements, the current at the end of the drop (*i.e.* the maximum current) was recorded. Saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode. Electrocapillary curves were obtained by drop-time method⁴. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 1.0 M $NaNO_3$, open circuit): $m=2.6$ mg/s, $t=3.0$ s, $m^{2/3} t^{1/3}=2.27$ mg^{2/3} s^{-1/3}, $h_{corr}=42.3$ cm.

The following cationic and anionic surfactants were used: cationic: LPC, CPC, CPB, CTAB, and CDBAC; anionic: SLS, Manoxol-OT, Tergitol-7 and DBS; mixtures: LPC+SLS, LPC+Manoxol-OT, LPC+Tergitol-7, LPC+DBS, CPC+SLS, CPC+Manoxol-OT, CPC+Tergitol-7, CPC+DBS, CPB+SLS, CPB+Manoxol-OT, CPB+Tergitol-7, CPB+DBS, CTAB+SLS, CTAB+Manoxol-OT, CTAB+Tergitol-7, CTAB+DBS, CDBAC+SLS, CDBAC+Manoxol-OT, CDBAC+Tergitol-7 and CDBAC+DBS.

Results and Discussion

Tl^{I} under the chosen experimental conditions, yields a sharp maximum which lies at -0.56 V (*vs* S.C.E.) near the potential of the electrocapillary zero, which is -0.51 V (S.C.E.) under the same experimental conditions. Since the $E_{x/2}$ value (≈ -0.485 V) of Tl^{I} lies on the positive side of the electrocapillary zero, the maximum of Tl^{I} is of positive polarity⁵. The effect of increasing concentrations of cationic and anionic surfactants, separately and in their mixtures, on E_{max} and i_{max} has been studied. It is seen that E_{max} gets shifted to less negative potentials (positive shift) as the concentration of the surfactants is increased. The i_{max} decreases from $38.0 \mu A$ (in the absence of surfactants) to different values just before the suppression of the maximum. The M.S.P. values for different surfactants, separately and in their mixtures, have been determined⁶ and are listed in Table 1. On the basis of M.S.P. values, the suppressive powers of the surfactants follow the order: CDBAC >

CPB > CPC > LPC > CTAB (cationic); SLS > Tergitol-7 > Manoxol-OT > DBS (anionic). A perusal of Table 1 shows that though the M.S.P. values for cationic and anionic surfactants are slightly different yet the fact remains that the same order of magnitude *i.e.* 10^{-6} or $10^{-5} M$, exists for their M.S.P. values. It is thus inferred that both cationic and anionic surfactants are effective in suppressing the positive maximum of Tl^{I} almost to the same extent. This may be due to the proximity of this maximum from the potential of the electrocapillary zero. Thus, the Heyrovsky generalisation^{7,8} does not hold good with regard to the positive maximum of Tl^{I} .

TABLE 1—COMPARATIVE VALUES OF M. S. P. FOR THE MAXIMUM OF Tl^{I} , IN RESPECT OF CATIONIC AND ANIONIC SURFACTANTS SEPARATELY AND IN THEIR MIXTURES

Surfactant	M. S. P. <i>M</i>	Cationic + Anionic surfactants	M. S. P. <i>M</i>
Cationic			
LPC	8.96×10^{-6}	LPC+SLS	2.84×10^{-6}
OPC	7.94×10^{-6}	LPC+Manoxol-OT	7.39×10^{-6}
OPB	5.96×10^{-6}	LPC+Tergitol-7	6.45×10^{-6}
CTAB	9.98×10^{-6}	LPC+DBS	6.39×10^{-6}
CDBAC	4.92×10^{-6}	OPC+SLS	4.35×10^{-6}
Anionic			
SLS	7.95×10^{-6}	OPC+Manoxol-OT	4.02×10^{-6}
Manoxol-OT	6.25×10^{-6}	OPC+Tergitol-7	8.41×10^{-6}
Tergitol-7	4.93×10^{-6}	OPC+DBS	4.42×10^{-6}
DBS	7.94×10^{-6}	OPB+SLS	3.75×10^{-6}
		OPB+Manoxol-OT	4.74×10^{-6}
		OPB+Tergitol-7	8.89×10^{-6}
		OPB+DBS	6.22×10^{-6}
		CTAB+SLS	5.38×10^{-6}
		CTAB+Manoxol-OT	4.95×10^{-6}
		CTAB+Tergitol-7	8.86×10^{-6}
		CTAB+DBS	8.44×10^{-6}
		CDBAC+SLS	3.01×10^{-6}
		CDBAC+Manoxol-OT	4.67×10^{-6}
		CDBAC+Tergitol-7	6.41×10^{-6}
		CDBAC+DBS	8.22×10^{-6}

The electrocapillary curves in the presence of different concentrations of cationic and anionic surfactants, separately and in their mixtures, are shown in Fig. 1. In the absence of surfactant, the potential of electrocapillary zero is -0.51 V (*vs* S.C.E.) under the chosen experimental conditions. But it gets shifted to more positive value in the presence of cationic surfactants and to more negative values in the presence of anionic surfactants. However, in case of mixtures of the two, this shift occurs either to more positive or to more negative potentials. The values of interfacial tension, obtained from electrocapillary curves for a certain potential (-0.40 V), have been obtained and it is seen that interfacial tension (γ) decreases with increasing concentrations of the surfactants. This implies positive adsorption as shown by the increasing positive values of ΓRT calculated by Gibbs' adsorption equation,

$$\Gamma = -\frac{C}{RT} \frac{d\gamma}{dC}$$

Fig. 1. Electrocapillary curves of Tl^{I} in the presence of (a) LPC: (1) 0.0, (2) 5.0×10^{-7} , (3) 1.0×10^{-6} , (4) 3.0×10^{-6} , (5) 7.0×10^{-6} and (6) 9.0×10^{-6} M; (b) SLS: (1) 0.0, (2) 5.0×10^{-7} , (3) 1.0×10^{-6} , (4) 3.0×10^{-6} , (5) 6.0×10^{-6} and (6) 8.0×10^{-6} M; (c) LPC+SLS: (1) 0.0, (2) $4.0 \times 10^{-7} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$, (3) $6.0 \times 10^{-7} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$, (4) $1.0 \times 10^{-6} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$, (5) $2.0 \times 10^{-6} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$ and (6) $3.0 \times 10^{-6} + 4.0 \times 10^{-7}$ M.

The values of $d\gamma/dC$ have been obtained from γ vs C plots.

The additive and antagonistic effects of mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants have been ascertained by determining their M.S.P. values, separately and in their mixtures. A comparison of the M.S.P. values in the two cases provides information as to the antagonistic or additive effects of mixtures of cationic and anionic surfactants in the suppression of positive maximum of Tl^{I} . The M.S.P. values in respect of various surfactants and their mixtures have been determined and listed in Table 1. A perusal of this Table shows that the M.S.P. values in respect of the mixtures, LPC+SLS, LPC+Manoxol-OT, LPC+Tergitol-7, LPC+DBS, CPC+SLS, CPC+Tergitol-7, CPB+SLS, CPB+Tergitol-7, CTAB+SLS, CTAB+Tergitol-7, CDBAC+SLS and CDBAC+Tergitol-7, are smaller than those for individual surfactants, thereby indicating additive effects of these mixtures in the suppression of positive maximum of Tl^{I} . This is further supported by the fact that the values of ΓRT at the stage of just suppression of the maximum are larger for the above mentioned mixtures than those for the individual surfactants. However, in the case of the mixtures, CPC+Manoxol-OT, CPC+DBS, CPB+Manoxol-OT, CPB+DBS, CTAB+Manoxol-OT, CTAB+DBS, CDBAC+Manoxol-OT and CDBAC+DBS, the M.S.P. values are higher than those for the individual surfactants, thereby showing the antagonistic effects in the suppression of the maximum of Tl^{I} . This is supported by the smaller values of ΓRT at the stage of just suppression of the maximum.

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References

1. S. LAL and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 898.
2. S. LAL and S. N. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, **7**, 332.
3. G. RAM, Ph. D. Thesis, Agra University, 1978.
4. P. ZUMAN and I. M. KOLTHOFF, "Progress in Polarography", Interscience, New York, 1962, Vol. I, p. 88.
5. J. HEYROVSKY and J. KUTA, "Principles of Polarography", Academic, New York, 1966, p. 437.
6. E. L. COLICHMAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4036.
7. J. HEYROVSKY, "A Polarographic Study of the Electrokinetic Phenomena of Adsorption, Electroreduction and Overpotential displayed at the Dropping Mercury Cathode", *Actualites Scientifiques et industrielles*, Paris, 1934, No. 90.
8. J. HEYROVSKY, in "Die Physikalischen Methoden der Chemischen Analyse", ed. W. BORRGER, Leipzig, 1936, Vol. 2, pp. 266-282.

Occurrence of 7,8-Epoxy-5,6-dehydrokawain in *Didymocarpus podocarpa*

A. K. DAS*

North Bengal Campus, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Coochbehar-736 101

and

ANJAN BHATTACHARYYA and S. R. MITRA

Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235

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CHEMICAL investigation on two *Didymocarpus* species *D. pedicellata* and *D. aurentiaca* led to the isolation of a number of chalcones¹⁻⁴, quinochalcones⁵, flavanones^{6,7}, terpenoids⁸, and α -pyrones⁹.

* Present address: Department of Agricultural Chemistry & Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235.